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Deliverable 4 - Report on the development, comparison and validation of sampling systems (using back-to-back sampling and repeated sampling)

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Summary

Hydrogen fuel quality is essential for the durability and reliability of fuel cell systems, particularly in heavy-duty (HD) vehicles operating under demanding conditions. Ensuring compliance with purity standards requires validated sampling systems at hydrogen refuelling stations. While established methods exist for light-duty (LD) refuelling, their suitability for HD applications has not been fully proven.

This study evaluates three sampling systems (DirSAM, ENGIE sampler, and HySaM) through back-to-back HD refuelling experiments and comparison with LD configurations. Most gaseous impurities specified in ISO 14687:2025 showed statistical equivalence across systems within measurement uncertainties. Differences in nitrogen, water, and sulfur were system-dependent without consistent bias. LD sampling was found unreliable for representing HD conditions, particularly regarding water. No correlation was observed between particulate matter and dispensed hydrogen or vehicle state of charge.

These results support adapting existing sampling methods to HD refuelling while highlighting the need for further validation and standard development.

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Abstract:	Hydrogen fuel quality is essential for the durability and reliability of fuel cell systems, particularly in heavy-duty (HD) vehicles operating under demanding conditions. Ensuring compliance with purity standards requires validated sampling systems at hydrogen refuelling stations. While established methods exist for light-duty (LD) refuelling, their suitability for HD applications has not been fully proven. This study evaluates three sampling systems (DirSAM, ENGIE sampler, and HySaM) through back-to-back HD refuelling experiments and comparison with LD configurations. Most gaseous impurities specified in ISO 14687:2025 showed statistical equivalence across systems within measurement uncertainties. Differences in nitrogen, water, and sulfur were system-dependent without consistent bias. LD sampling was found unreliable for representing HD conditions, particularly regarding water. No correlation was observed between particulate matter and dispensed hydrogen or vehicle state of charge. These results support adapting existing sampling methods to HD refuelling while highlighting the need for further validation and standard development.

Equivalence Assessment of Hydrogen Sampling Systems for Heavy-Duty Refuelling Applications

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Abstract

Keywords: hydrogen fuel quality; heavy-duty transport; sampling validation; hydrogen refuelling station; ISO 14687

1. Introduction

Hydrogen is widely recognised as a key energy carrier for achieving climate-neutral transport systems in Europe by 2050, particularly in segments that are difficult to electrify directly, such as heavy-duty (HD) road transport [1] [2] [3] [4]. In contrast to battery-electric solutions, hydrogen fuel-cell electric vehicles (FCEVs) offer high gravimetric energy density, long driving ranges, and rapid refuelling, making them well suited for long-haul trucking, buses, and high-utilisation fleet operations [2] [5] [6] [7]. These advantages have positioned hydrogen as a key technology in European decarbonisation strategies for HD transport corridors and logistics hubs [3] [4] [8]. Unlike light-duty (LD) FCEVs, HD vehicles are typically engineered and designed for substantially longer service lifetimes, often exceeding 20,000-30,000 operating hours and operate under higher loads and more demanding duty cycles [6]. Under these conditions, prolonged exposure to trace impurities such as sulfur-containing compounds,

1 carbon monoxide, and ammonia can significantly accelerate catalyst poisoning, membrane
2 degradation, and irreversible performance losses in proton exchange membrane fuel cells
3 (PEMFCs) [9]. Consequently, stringent hydrogen quality assurance is of particular importance
4 for HD applications, where premature fuel-cell degradation can lead to substantial economic
5 losses and operational disruptions [10] [11] [9]. Hydrogen purity specifications for road
6 transport are defined in ISO 14687:2025 [12] and EN 17124:2022 [13], which set stringent
7 limits for thirteen different gaseous contaminants and particulate matter due to their detrimental
8 effects on fuel-cell components, including catalysts and polymer electrolyte membranes.
9 Compliance with these specifications relies not only on robust analytical techniques but also
10 on representative sampling of the hydrogen dispensed at HRS nozzles.

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14 Sampling methodologies described in ISO 19880-9 were primarily developed for LD refuelling
15 stations. Two main sampling strategies are commonly applied for hydrogen quality assessment:
16 direct and parallel sampling [14]. In direct sampling, hydrogen is withdrawn directly into a
17 dedicated sampling cylinder. Sampling systems using this approach generally require control
18 over refuelling conditions and may involve operating the HRS in either service or maintenance
19 mode. In some configurations, an intermediate buffer tank can be incorporated to avoid
20 overriding the station's refuelling protocol. In contrast, parallel sampling fills the sampling
21 cylinder simultaneously with a FCEV or a surrogate receptacle via a tee connection, thereby
22 maintaining normal refuelling operation without bypassing safety systems. However, HD
23 refuelling introduces additional challenges, including higher mass flow rates, larger dispensed
24 volumes, different refuelling protocols (e.g., SAE J2601-5 [15]), and modified nozzle
25 geometries. These factors can affect both gas composition and interactions between
26 contaminants and sampling systems. Although a number of sampling systems originally
27 developed for LD applications have been adapted for use under HD conditions and other new
28 systems have been designed specifically for HD refuelling, their performance cannot be
29 assumed a priori. Dedicated validation is therefore required to demonstrate their
30 representativity and comparability under HD operating conditions.

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39 Validation of hydrogen sampling systems is inherently challenging because the "true"
40 composition of the total dispensed fuel cannot be directly measured. In the absence of reference
41 methods capable of analysing the full delivered hydrogen quantity, equivalence testing based
42 on comparative measurements using multiple sampling systems under identical conditions
43 provides a pragmatic approach. If multiple systems yield statistically consistent results,
44 confidence in their representativity is increased, although trueness cannot be directly
45 established.

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50 This study presents a comparative assessment of three sampling systems adapted for HD
51 hydrogen refuelling, conducted within the MetHyTrucks project [16]. The work focuses on (i)
52 equivalence of sampling systems for gaseous contaminants, (ii) comparison between LD and
53 HD sampling configurations, and (iii) assessment of particulate matter sampling under HD
54 refuelling conditions.

55 56 57 58 **2. Sampling Systems**

59 60 **Sampling of Gaseous Species**

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Three sampling systems were evaluated:

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2 NPL DirSAM: a direct nozzle-mounted sampling system based on ASTM D7606-17, designed
3 for both LD and HD refuelling and capable of operating at flow rates up to $120 \text{ g}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and
4 pressures up to 35 MPa [6]. Sampled hydrogen is vented via an exhaust stack.
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7 ENGIE sampling device: a system adaptable for 35 and 70 MPa refuelling that allows online
8 monitoring of oxygen and water during refuelling events. Unlike other direct sampling
9 approaches, it does not require manual override of HRS safety protocols. The strategy can be
10 considered as a parallel sampling system due to the presence of a 55L cylinder fitted to the
11 sampling equipment. It is worth noting that, although the system operates in parallel, the
12 presence of a vehicle is not required.
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16 HySaM sampling system: a modular system comprising the sampling interface, a mobile vent,
17 and sampling cylinders (2.25 L or 10 L). It supports parallel and dead-end sampling at both 35
18 and 70 MPa and can be combined with particulate sampling.
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21 Detailed technical descriptions of the systems are provided elsewhere [17].
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23 **Sampling of particulate matter**

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25 Particulate matter was sampled using the HYDAC PSA-H70 high-pressure filter holder
26 (HYDAC, Sulzbach, Germany), installed in series between the HRS nozzle and the vehicle or
27 simulated tank system. Two variants (MC1 and MC2) were used, differing in pressure
28 protection and depressurisation strategy. The system is rated for pressures up to 70 MPa and
29 enables representative sampling without bypassing standard refuelling protocols.
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32 33 34 35 **3. Experimental Setup**

36 **Gaseous species sampling**

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39 Equivalence testing for gaseous contaminants was conducted at the ZBT Hydrogen Testfield
40 (Duisburg, Germany), which offers controlled HD refuelling at 35 MPa with well-characterised
41 impurity levels. comparison of fuel quality sampled through different refuelling lines.
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44 The ZBT Hydrogen Testfield, located in Duisburg, Germany, was selected for the HD sampling
45 equivalence experiments and for the comparison of the sampling using two nozzles (one for
46 LD- and one for HD-refuelling). The station was chosen for several reasons, including its
47 accessibility, its established experience with hydrogen sampling exercises during previous
48 projects (notably 19ENG04 MetroHyVe 2), and its suitable fuel composition. In particular, the
49 hydrogen dispensed at the station is known to contain measurable levels of selected impurities,
50 which is advantageous for the comparison of sampling systems.
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55 The testfield was commissioned in 2017 and has a total hydrogen storage capacity of
56 approximately 900 kg, distributed across storage banks at 30, 50 and 90 MPa. Hydrogen can
57 be dispensed at 35 or 70 MPa, and multiple refuelling protocols can be implemented, including
58 SAE J2601, MC Formula, PRHYDE, and freely configurable refuelling sequences. Within the
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European-funded RHeadHy project [18], high-flow infrastructure for 70 MPa heavy-duty hydrogen refuelling was installed, enabling peak mass flow rates of up to 300 g s⁻¹.

To assess whether LD sampling can represent HD refuelling, additional experiments were conducted using the HySaM system on both LD (70 MPa, SAE J2601-1) and HD (35 MPa, SAE J2601-5) nozzles supplied by identical storage banks.

The specific test parameters applied during the HD sampling equivalence experiments are summarised in Table 1 (comparable refuelling conditions using the three sampling systems in back-to-back configurations), the specific test parameters applied during sampling using two nozzles are summarised in Table 2.

These parameters were selected based on studies conducted within the MetHyTrucks project, which demonstrated that hydrogen sampling at refuelling stations is strongly influenced by operational conditions. The studies further showed that significant sampling bias can occur if sampling is not carried out in accordance with the recommended practices [18].

Table 1. Test parameters applied for HD sampling equivalence experiments

Sampling system	Sampling type	pressure line	Protocol	Precooling	Manual pressure setting	Storage bank
HySaM	Parallel	35 MPa HF	SAE J2601-5 (MFC-HF-G)	T20 (HX)	SAE J2601-5	Medium pressure (4+5)
ENGIE system	Parallel	35 MPa HF	SAE J2601-1	T20 (HX)	manually set APRR, 89 MPa/min (based on SAE)	Medium pressure (4+5)
NPL DuSam	Direct	35 MPa HF	Maintenance	T20 (HX)	Manually set at 20 MPa	Medium pressure (4+5)

Table 2. Test parameters applied for the comparison HD versus LD sampling for HySaM (n.a.: not applicable)

Test #	Sampling system	Sampling type	Protocol	Bank	Sink	Precooling	HX
Storage bank 6	HySaM	Direct	-	6	none	n.a.	n.a.
Storage bank 7	HySaM	Direct	-	7	none	n.a.	n.a.
LD sampling	HySaM	Parallel	SAE 2601-1	6+7	Hexagon (244 L)	T20	Plate
HD sampling	HySaM	Parallel	SAE 2601-5	6+7	NPROXX (341 L)	T20	Plate

Particulate Matter sampling

Particulate sampling was carried out at an alternative HD-HRS known for measurable particulate levels. Sampling was performed under standard refuelling protocols, with maximum mass flow rates limited to 60 g·s⁻¹ as a precaution. Collected filters were analysed gravimetrically and further characterised using SEM-EDS and ICP-MS.

1 Test stations and test parameters

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3 An alternative HD-HRS was chosen for particulate matter sampling because of its history of
4 quantifiable amounts of particulate matter in dispensed fuel. H35 and H70 dispensers were
5 available for sampling. The HRS hub is a European publicly accessible multi-fuel station
6 offering low- and zero-carbon fuels including a refuelling station for cars operating at 70 and
7 35 MPa, two HD nozzles at 35 MPa. During the tests, a FCEV was available for H70 sampling
8 as well as several buses for H35.
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10 11 12 13 14 4. Analytical Methods

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16 Gaseous contaminants were analysed primarily by NPL using ISO/IEC 17025-accredited
17 internal methods covering all species listed in ISO 14687:2025 [12]. Calibration employed
18 primary reference materials in hydrogen matrices, and uncertainties were evaluated using
19 NPL's XLGENline software. Details on the analytical methods are provided below. Oxygen
20 and argon were analysed by gas chromatography (Agilent Technologies, USA) coupled with a
21 pulsed discharge helium ionization detector (PDHID, VICI) using helium as a carrier gas. The
22 GC/PDHID sampling loop was 1 ml. The sample was transferred onto capillary column
23 Molsieve 5A plot (30 m x 0.53 mm x 50 µm) and a second capillary column Molsieve 5A plot
24 (50 m x 0.53 mm x 50 µm). The GC oven was set at 30 degrees Celsius. Methane, carbon
25 monoxide, carbon dioxide and non-methane hydrocarbons were measured by GC (Peak
26 Laboratories, US) coupled with a methaniser FID. The method used a Hayesep D column (186"
27 x 1.5") with nitrogen carrier with the column held at a temperature of 65 degrees Celsius. The
28 loop size used for sample injection was 5 ml. Total sulphur compounds were measured by gas
29 chromatography with sulphur chemiluminescence detector (GC-SCD). The analysis of the
30 sample is performed on an Agilent 7890A gas chromatograph (Agilent, USA) equipped with
31 two detectors, a flame ionization detector and sulfur chemiluminescence detector (SCD 355,
32 Agilent Technologies, USA). The GC-SCD sampling loop volume was 1 ml. The sample was
33 then transferred onto capillary column used which is a HP-5, 30 m x 0.320 mm ID x 0.251 µm
34 film thickness (Agilent, USA). The column program temperature is isothermal at 110 °C.
35 Helium is used as a carrier gas at a flow rate of 20 ml/min. Organo-halogenated compounds
36 were analysed using a TD-GC (Markes International, UK) coupled with mass spectroscopy
37 (MS) with a split FID (Agilent Technologies, UK). The compounds were adsorbed onto
38 chromosorb tube. This system desorbs the analytes from the sorbent and releases the analytes
39 onto a U-T6SUL cold trap. A DB-VRX column 60m x 0.25mm with a helium carrier was used
40 for separation. Nitrogen and helium compounds were measured by micro gas chromatography
41 with thermal conductivity detector (µGC-TCD). The analysis of the sample is performed on an
42 Agilent 990 microGC (Agilent, USA) with PLOT column Molsieve 5A (10 m x 0.25 mm OD
43 x 30µm ID) and 3 m guard column equipped with thermal conductivity detector. Hydrogen is
44 used as carrier gas. The analysis of ammonia, formic acid and formaldehyde were realised
45 using optical feedback cavity enhanced absorption spectroscopy (OFCEAS). The analyses
46 were done using an Optical Feedback Cavity Enhanced Absorption Spectroscopy from AP2E
47 (PROCEAS, Durag group, Aix-en-Provence, France). Water analysis was realised using cavity
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1 ring down spectroscopy (CRDS) using TigerOptic Spark (TigerOptic, Warrington, PA, USA).
2 The flow was maintained around 300 ml/min until stable reading.

3 For the comparison of LD and HD samples, selected gas analyses, specifically water and
4 nitrogen, were conducted at ZBT using quartz crystal microbalance (QCM) measurements and
5 mass spectrometry. Nitrogen concentrations were determined using a CombiSense system
6 manufactured by V&F Analyse- und Messtechnik GmbH. Gas samples were continuously
7 extracted from the bypass line at a flow rate of 350 mL min⁻¹.
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10 Water concentrations were measured using a QMA401 quartz crystal microbalance analyzer
11 manufactured by Michell Instruments (UK). Gas samples were drawn directly from the gas
12 cylinder to the analyzer, and the sample flow was regulated by system pressure (1 bar
13 overpressure), resulting in a constant flow rate of 0.400 L min⁻¹ during the measurements. The
14 complete measurement setup was optimized to minimize possible adsorption. All surfaces that
15 are in contact with gas were coated with SilcoNert 2000, an inert silicon-based coating to
16 minimize surface interactions and contamination effects. To prevent accumulation or
17 backdiffusion of atmospheric impurities within the gas lines, the entire system was
18 continuously purged with high-purity hydrogen (purity grade 9.0) and maintained at an
19 overpressure of 1 bar. The reported uncertainties represent expanded uncertainties with a
20 coverage factor of $k = 2$, corresponding to an approximate confidence level of 95%.
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27 PTFE particulate filters were conditioned and weighed before and after sampling using a
28 gravimetric approach in a controlled laboratory environment with constant temperature and
29 relative humidity. The mass difference was used to determine the particulate loading on each
30 filter.
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33 Following gravimetric determination, filters were characterised for particle morphology and
34 elemental composition using a Zeiss Auriga 60 focused ion beam-scanning electron
35 microscope (FIB-SEM) acquiring electron images using the In-Lense detector. Energy
36 Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) elemental maps and line scans were acquired on the
37 same SEM with an Oxford Instruments X-max 80 detector at an accelerating voltage of 20 kV.
38 A PTFE blank filter was analysed to assess background contributions arising from the filter
39 substrate. For each sample, two distinct filter regions were examined to assess potential spatial
40 heterogeneity: (i) the central deposition area and (ii) the edge region of the filter. From each
41 region, a 5 mm × 5 mm section was excised for analysis.
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47 Each filter section was mounted on 8 mm aluminium SEM stubs and sputter-coated with a 15
48 nm layer of gold to ensure sufficient electrical conductivity for SEM-EDS analysis. The
49 presence of gold was observed in all EDS spectra; however, it was excluded from elemental
50 weight-percentage calculations to avoid interference or misinterpretation, particularly with any
51 overlapping sulfur X-ray peaks.
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55 Following SEM-EDS characterisation, bulk elemental composition of the particulate matter
56 was determined by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). The filters were
57 transferred into PTFE microwave vials and acid digested in a Milestone microwave at 200°C,
58 after addition of a mixture of 65% HNO₃ and 37% HCl (ratio 1:1). After digestion, samples
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1 were diluted with Milli-Q water in 50 mL MetalFree® vials, and then further diluted 10 times
2 with 5% HNO₃ before analysis.

3 Samples were analyzed using an Agilent 8900 ICP-MS/MS, equipped with a multi-quadrupole
4 ICP-MS system with collision/reaction cell technology. The samples are injected into the
5 system with an SDS-4 autosampler combined with an Integrated Sample Introduction System;
6 the sample loop volume allows discreet volume injection, high-speed sample uptake, and rapid
7 washout. The introduction system further includes quartz torch, and nickel sample and skimmer
8 cones.
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10 On-mass and mass-shift modes were selected in the triple quadrupole to eliminate polyatomic
11 interferences. Analyte elements were selected with four different gas modes: no-gas, helium
12 on-mass, oxygen on-mass, and oxygen in mass-shift reaction mode. The mode with the highest
13 sensitivity, best interferences reduction, and lowest instrumental relative standard deviation
14 (RSD%) is chosen and accuracy is evaluated using reference materials and quality controls. A
15 7-points calibration curve was prepared using multi-element standards from Inorganic
16 Ventures, with concentrations ranging from 0 to 500 nmol mol⁻¹. A 400 nmol mol⁻¹ indium
17 solution was used as internal standard to monitor instrument stability and plasma robustness
18 throughout the analysis. The raw data was then converted from ng/mL to mg kg⁻¹, based on
19 dilution factors and sample weight. A concentration relative standard deviation (Conc. RSD)
20 was calculated across four replicates to ensure statistical robustness and account for any sample
21 heterogeneity.
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32 5. Results and Discussion

33 Sampling repeatability

34 For each sampling system, repeatability was evaluated from the standard deviation of two
35 sampling events carried out on the same day. The results are presented in Table 3.
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38 Table 3. Results of repeatability sampling for each sampling systems. The results are reported with reference to
39 the nominal amount fraction of each chemical compounds. The values in *italic* are above 10% relative.
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Compound	Nominal value	Sampling systems		
		NPL DirSAM (Direct)	ENGIE sampler (Parallel)	HySaM (Parallel)
		Repeatability in %		
O ₂	0.2 - 0.4 μmol mol ⁻¹	10.9	14.6	17.4
CO	0.008 - 0.010 μmol mol ⁻¹	0.58	5.05	1.63
CO ₂	0.23 - 0.26 μmol mol ⁻¹	0.20	0.20	0.28
Ar	1.8 - 2.0 μmol mol ⁻¹	1.60	0.94	2.60
He	25 - 28 μmol mol ⁻¹	4.13	0.43	0.59
Total non-methane hydrocarbons	8 - 16 nmol mol ⁻¹	42.4	14.6	4.1
N ₂	850 - 900 μmol mol ⁻¹	0.17	1.12	0.89
H ₂ O	4 - 9 μmol mol ⁻¹	1.3	2.6	18.5
Total Sulfur	0.5 - 5.0 nmol mol ⁻¹	4.9	4.5	9.2

Overall, the repeatability of the sampling systems was below 10 % relative for most compounds, which is considered satisfactory. An exception was observed for oxygen, where repeatability values exceeded 10 % for all three sampling systems. The consistently low repeatability values obtained for N₂, Ar, He, and CO₂ reflect the robustness of both the sampling systems and the analytical methods at the relatively high nominal amount fractions of these compounds for the analytical technique employed.

However, the nominal oxygen amount fraction was very low (0.2–0.4 μmol mol⁻¹) and the associated analytical uncertainty was relatively high (10–15%). Consequently, the observed variability in oxygen repeatability is likely influenced primarily by measurement uncertainty rather than by the sampling process itself. Similarly, the elevated repeatability values observed for NMHC in some cases are most likely influenced by the low concentration level and analytical limitations, rather than reflecting a systematic limitation of the sampling systems. However further study may be required to investigate if similar behaviour is observed a higher amount fraction closer to ISO 14687:2025 threshold.

It should be noted that the direct sampling systems exhibited better repeatability for compounds that are sensitive to hydrogen refuelling station (HRS) operating parameters, such as water and nitrogen. Consequently, the observed improvement in repeatability is not necessarily attributable to the sampling hardware itself, but rather to the sampling strategy, which imposes more tightly controlled HRS operating conditions and thereby reduces operational variability.

Equivalence of gaseous sampling systems

The results of the sampling system equivalence study are summarised in Table 4. The evaluation was performed by comparing the average values of two sampling events obtained with each sampling system and assessing their agreement using the combined expanded measurement uncertainties, in accordance with the following equation:

$$|\bar{x}_{\text{samp1,d1}} - \bar{x}_{\text{samp2,d1}}| < 2 \times \sqrt{u_{\text{samp1,d1}}^2 + u_{\text{samp2,d1}}^2}$$

With

$\bar{x}_{\text{samp1,d1}}$ being the mean value of the two samplings of sampling system 1 on day 1

$\bar{x}_{\text{samp2,d1}}$ being the mean value of the two samplings of sampling system 2 on day 1

$u_{\text{samp1,d1}}^2$ being the combined uncertainty of the two samplings of sampling system 1 on day 1

$u_{\text{samp2,d1}}^2$ being the combined uncertainty of the two samplings of sampling system 2 on day 1

Table 4. Results of equivalence between the different HD sampling system tested in the study. = means equivalent (with 95% confidence level, k factor evaluated to 2) and ≠ means significantly different.

Compound	Sampling systems		
	NPL DirSAM	ENGIE sampler	HySaM

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O ₂	=	=	=
CO	=	=	=
CO ₂	=	=	=
Ar	=	=	=
He	=	=	=
Total non-methane hydrocarbons	=	=	=
N ₂	=	=	≠
H ₂ O	=	≠	=
Total Sulfur	≠	=	=

Across the majority of analysed contaminants (O₂, CO, CO₂, Ar, He, NMHC), the three sampling systems showed statistical equivalence within combined expanded uncertainties (k = 2).

For nitrogen, water, and total sulfur, one system in each case showed disagreement with the other two. As the deviating system varied by compound, no systematic bias could be identified. These findings highlight that equivalence does not imply trueness, but rather mutual consistency under the tested conditions.

Notably, total sulfur measurements differed substantially between DirSAM and the ENGIE/HySaM systems, with DirSAM reporting values near the EN 17124 limit. This divergence warrants further investigation into potential adsorption or desorption effects related to materials or sampling cylinders.

The results are also presented in Figures 1 to 9.

Figure 1. Amount fraction of nitrogen obtained for the three systems during the validation exercise and two different days. Expanded uncertainties are provided with k=2.

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Figure 2. Amount fraction of water obtained for the three systems during the validation exercise and two different days. Expanded uncertainties are provided with $k=2$.

Figure 3. Amount fraction of sulfur obtained for the three systems during the validation exercise and two different days. Expanded uncertainties are provided with $k=2$.

Figure 4. Amount fraction of oxygen obtained for the three systems during the validation exercise and two different days. Expanded uncertainties are provided with $k=2$.

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Figure 5. Amount fraction of carbon monoxide obtained for the three systems during the validation exercise and two different days. Expanded uncertainties are provided with $k=2$.

Figure 6. Amount fraction of carbon dioxide obtained for the three systems during the validation exercise and two different days. Expanded uncertainties are provided with $k=2$.

Figure 7. Amount fraction of argon obtained for the three systems during the validation exercise and two different days. Expanded uncertainties are provided with $k=2$.

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Figure 8. Amount fraction of helium obtained for the three systems during the validation exercise and two different

Figure 9. Amount fraction of non-methane hydrocarbons obtained for the three systems during the validation exercise and two different days. Expanded uncertainties are provided with $k=2$.

The results for the nitrogen amount-fraction (Figure 1) show good agreement between the NPL DirSAM and ENGIE sampling systems, whereas the HySaM system exhibited statistically significant disagreement relative to both NPL DirSAM and ENGIE. A comparison between measurements performed on day 1 and day 2 indicates that the nitrogen amount fraction remained stable over time; however, the disagreement between NPL DirSAM and HySaM persisted on both sampling days.

For water (Figure 2), the results demonstrate good statistical agreement between NPL DirSAM and HySaM, while the ENGIE system exhibited statistically significant disagreement with both systems. In contrast to nitrogen, the water amount fraction showed variability between day 1 and day 2. Despite this temporal variability, the agreement between NPL DirSAM and HySaM was maintained across both sampling days.

As noted previously, equivalence does not imply trueness. These results should therefore be interpreted with caution when drawing conclusions regarding the true amount fraction and representativity of the sampled hydrogen. The outcomes nevertheless provide an initial insight into the relative performance of the sampling systems. Elevated water amount fractions are commonly associated with insufficient purging or leakage; consequently, further investigations would be required to establish the true water concentration and to discriminate more conclusively between the performance of the sampling systems. It should also be noted that the

1 largest changes in repeatability were observed for the HySaM system. As this system operates
2 in parallel with the refuelling protocol, the observed variability may reflect variations in HRS
3 refuelling conditions rather than intrinsic characteristics of the sampling hardware itself.
4 Additional studies may therefore be required to provide clearer guidance on the use of parallel
5 sampling strategies.
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7 For total sulfur (Figure 3), good statistical agreement was observed between the ENGIE and
8 HySaM systems, whereas the NPL DirSAM system showed statistically significant
9 disagreement with both. The sulfur amount fraction remained stable between day 1 and day 2;
10 however, the disagreement between NPL DirSAM and the other two systems persisted on both
11 days. A clear separation was observed between the results obtained with NPL DirSAM and
12 those from ENGIE and HySaM. NPL DirSAM consistently reported higher sulfur values (4 –
13 5 nmol mol⁻¹), while ENGIE and HySaM reported values below 1 nmol mol⁻¹, with
14 overlapping measurement uncertainties. This divergence is particularly important given that
15 EN 17124 specifies a sulfur threshold of 4 nmol mol⁻¹. Consequently, further investigation is
16 warranted to determine whether the NPL DirSAM results reflect a positive bias or whether the
17 ENGIE and HySaM systems exhibit a negative bias. Such investigations may need to consider
18 specific sampling-system components, such as cylinder type and surface materials, to better
19 understand the origin of the observed discrepancies.
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26 For oxygen (Figure 4), all three sampling systems (ENGIE, NPL DirSAM, and HySaM)
27 showed good statistical agreement. However, relatively large fluctuations in oxygen amount
28 fraction were observed. These fluctuations are likely attributable to analytical limitations, as
29 the measurement techniques employed had limits of detection on the order of 0.1 μmol mol⁻¹.
30 To improve discrimination between sampling systems for oxygen, future studies should
31 consider experiments at higher oxygen amount fractions or the use of analytical methods with
32 improved sensitivity.
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37 The results for carbon monoxide (Figure 5) showed good statistical agreement among ENGIE,
38 NPL DirSAM, and HySaM. In addition, comparison between day 1 and day 2 demonstrated
39 stable CO amount fractions over time, indicating that neither HRS operating conditions nor
40 sampling procedures introduced detectable bias.
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43 Similarly, for carbon dioxide (Figure 6), all three sampling systems displayed good statistical
44 agreement, with no significant day-to-day variation observed. This stability suggests robust
45 sampling and analytical performance for CO₂ under the tested conditions.
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48 For argon (Figure 7), all three systems yielded values within the same measurement range, with
49 no statistically significant differences. The argon amount fraction remained stable between
50 day 1 and day 2, indicating neither HRS operation nor sampling procedures affected the results.
51 As argon is an inert species exhibiting inherently stable behaviour in hydrogen fuel, these
52 observations provide strong evidence of equivalence between the sampling systems.
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56 Comparable results were obtained for helium (Figure 8), with good agreement between all three
57 sampling systems and no measurable day-to-day variation. The consistency of the helium data
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further supports the conclusion that the sampling systems performed equivalently for this compound.

Finally, for total non-methane hydrocarbons (Figure 9), ENGIE, NPL DirSAM, and HySaM exhibited good statistical agreement. Although increased variability was observed in some cases, this is likely influenced by the low nominal amount fractions and the nature of the NMHC measurement rather than reflecting a systematic limitation of the sampling systems.

Comparison of LD and HD Sampling

With the emergence of diverse refuelling concepts such as twin-nozzle dispensers, maritime and rail applications, and additional safety requirements related to geometry or communication interfaces—it is essential to assess whether a single sampling approach can adequately represent the hydrogen dispensed by an HRS. The results of the HD-LD sampling protocol comparison are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Test parameters applied for the comparison HD/LD. The uncertainty provided is with coverage factor of 2

Test #	protocol	Bank	Duration [min]	Average mass flow [g s ⁻¹]	Peak mass flow [g s ⁻¹]	Water amount fraction [μmol mol ⁻¹]	Nitrogen amount fraction [μmol mol ⁻¹]
Storage bank 6	-	6	-	-	-	11.15 ± 0.22	2550 ± 81
Storage bank 7	-	7	-	-	-	11.98 ± 0.24	2308 ± 73
LD sampling	SAE 2601-1	6+7	3:47	33.4	50.95	21.17 ± 0.43	2504 ± 80
HD sampling	SAE 2601-5	6+7	4:34	25.7	33.8	11.96 ± 0.24	2502 ± 80

According to Table 5, a difference of approximately 250 μmol mol⁻¹ in nitrogen amount fraction was observed between the two storage banks. The hydrogen sampled using both LD and HD configurations shows very good agreement, indicating that both sampling approaches captured the same hydrogen fraction originating from storage banks 6 and 7. For storage bank 6, the nitrogen amount fractions obtained from LD and HD sampling are in good statistical agreement. In contrast, the nitrogen amount fraction measured in storage bank 7 is significantly lower than the values obtained for LD sampling, HD sampling, and storage bank 6. This observation indicates that storage bank 6 was the dominant source of hydrogen delivered during the refuelling events.

For water, the difference in amount fraction between storage banks 6 and 7 is less than 1 μmol mol⁻¹. Based on the nitrogen results, it would therefore be expected that the water amount fractions measured during both LD and HD samplings would be closer to the value observed in storage bank 6. However, this expectation is not fulfilled. The HD sampling results

1 agree more closely with the water concentration measured in storage bank 7, while LD
2 sampling yields a significantly higher value ($21.17 \pm 0.43 \mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$), nearly twice that
3 measured in either storage bank. This indicates that the elevated water content observed during
4 LD sampling is unlikely to originate from the storage banks themselves.
5

6 A more plausible explanation is therefore a transient, line-specific effect occurring during the
7 SAE J2601-1 refuelling test, which utilises a different refuelling branch corresponding to the
8 70 MPa line. Compared with the 35 MPa refuelling line used for HD sampling, this branch
9 includes an additional stainless-steel piping section of approximately 2 m, with one manual
10 valve, one check valve, two air-actuated valves, two pressure transmitters, and two temperature
11 transmitters, as well as a different hose and nozzle. Although standard purging procedures have
12 been shown to be sufficient in previous cases, the most plausible explanation is the presence of
13 residual water in the piping, hose, or nozzle. This interpretation is supported by the fact that all
14 samples were analysed using the same analytical procedure and that no rainfall occurred which
15 could have introduced water during mechanical connection of the sampling cylinders.
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17 These results may therefore require further validation or repetition to confirm that the observed
18 behaviour is not a station-specific artefact. One important outcome of this study is that LD and
19 HD nozzle sampling cannot be assumed to be equivalent. Consequently, using LD sampling
20 results to infer HD fuel quality, or vice versa, may lead to inappropriate conclusions. At this
21 stage, it is not considered reliable to extrapolate fuel quality results between LD and HD
22 refuelling configurations. Further experimental evidence is required to better understand and
23 quantify these differences.
24

25 Particulate Matter

26 For two experiments (EX 3 H70 and EX 7 H35), the dispenser display was recorded on video,
27 and instantaneous refuelling rates were subsequently estimated from the recorded data. These
28 measurements were performed while sampling with the HYDAC PSA-H70 MC1 particulate
29 sampler, therefore, the potential impact of the sampler on refuelling rate is unknown. The
30 estimates are shown in Figure 10.
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52 Figure 10. Estimated refuelling rate estimates: H70 max 43 g s^{-1} and H35 max 30 g s^{-1} .

53 For the H70 refuelling experiment (EX 3), the maximum observed refuelling rate was
54 approximately 43 g s^{-1} , whereas for the H35 refuelling experiment (EX 7), the maximum
55 refuelling rate reached approximately 30 g s^{-1} .
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58 The result of the gravimetric analysis is shown in Figure .
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Exp No	Nozzle	Filter	Sampler	Vehicle	average RR(g s ⁻¹)					SOC(%)					kgH ₂	mgkg ⁻¹	µg
					10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100			
2	H35LF	45	HYDACMK2	NNBus											5.78	0.28	1502
4	H35LF	40	HYDACMK2	ALIANNA											1.44	-0.32	-456
6	H35LF	41	HYDACMK2	AUMA											2.80	0.22	627
	H35LF	38	HYDACMK1	AUMA											7.59	0.08	624
7	H35LF	36	HYDACMK2	LOLA-ROSE											5.62	0.10	564
	H35LF	37	HYDACMK1	LOLA-ROSE	16.61										3.79	0.44	1681
1	H70LF	47	HYDACMK1	NEXO											2.18	1.05	2288
3	H70LF	46	HYDACMK1	NEXO	26.25										2.52	0.21	528
5	H70LF	39	HYDACMK1	NEXO											2.58	-0.78	2021

Figure 11. Experiments conducted with particulate matter sampling. Green and blue indicate HYDAC MC1 and MC2 versions.

Negative values were observed for experiments 4 and 5, and a single exceedance of the 1 mg kg⁻¹ tolerance limit was recorded for experiment 1. To aid interpretation of these results, three possible hypotheses are proposed:

- 1) Mass of particulate matter collected on the filter is assumed to be proportional to total mass of hydrogen that passes through the filter. This assumes a pressure dependence from the average pressure ramp rate which should be constant.
- 2) Particulate sampling shows a dependence of the vehicle SOC because the mass velocity increases with time as a result of increased density of the fluid in the tank.
- 3) Particulate sampling shows “start-effect” through initial flush-out of particulate matter in dispenser.

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Figure 12. Plots of kg H2 dispensed (top) vs ug sample and SOC vs. ug kg⁻¹ (bottom).

As shown in Figure 12, no correlation is observed between the mass of particulate matter collected on the filters and the total mass of hydrogen that passed through the filter. One possible explanation is that, during protocol-controlled refuelling events, the average pressure ramp rate (APRR) remains essentially constant, thereby limiting variability in particulate release mechanisms associated with pressure changes.

As illustrated in Figure 10, the hydrogen mass flow rate increases during the refuelling process and decreases toward the end of the event. To properly assess the respective influences of flow

rate and pressure on particulate mobilisation, dedicated experiments in which these parameters are independently and explicitly controlled would be required.

Similarly, no correlation is observed between the vehicle state of charge (SOC) and the particulate concentration normalised to dispensed hydrogen mass. With APRR remaining constant, the pressure difference between the source and sink is regulated by the refuelling protocol, such that the primary variable evolving during the refuelling event is the hydrogen flow rate. A pronounced “start-effect” would be expected to be more visible in shorter refuelling events, corresponding to lower dispensed hydrogen masses. While such an effect cannot be clearly demonstrated across the data set, a weak tendency is observed in some experiments (EX1, EX7-MC1, EX2, and possibly EX6-MC1), where the absolute particulate mass collected decreases with increasing hydrogen mass dispensed. This apparent trend may be influenced by the temporal evolution of the mass flow rate and therefore warrants further investigation using direct flow measurements.

It should also be noted that, for EX 1, corresponding to filter 45, the sampling procedure was restarted twice. This interruption may have contributed to the measured particulate load and suggests a possible contribution from a start-effect.

Filters 45, 47, 39, and 38 were visually inspected for the presence of debris. Visible debris was observed only on filter 45, appearing both at the centre and along the edges of the filter. Subsequent SEM analysis revealed the presence of debris on filters 45, 47, and 39, as illustrated in Figure 13.

Figure 13. SEM imaging of filters 45 (a) and 47 (b).

An overview of the observations is given in Table 6

Table 6. EDS element mapping of filters. – equals to no difference with blank filter composition

Filter	Centre	Edge
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45	S	Stainless steel, S, brass, Si
47	-	Stainless steel, Al, Si
39	-	Cu, S
38	-	-

The results indicate that particulate matter was predominantly located near the edges of the filters rather than at the centre. This non-uniform deposition pattern suggests that particle transport and deposition mechanisms may be influenced by local flow dynamics within the filter holder. A more detailed investigation of this spatial distribution could help to inform the selection of areas of interest for microscopy analyses and support improved planning of future filter characterisation protocols.

The ICP-MS results are summarized in Table .

Table 7. ICP-MS analysis of filters. Filter 33 was a blank filter.

Sample reference	Al mg kg ⁻¹	Si mg kg ⁻¹	S mg kg ⁻¹	Cr mg kg ⁻¹	Mn mg kg ⁻¹	Fe mg kg ⁻¹	Ni mg kg ⁻¹	Cu mg kg ⁻¹	Zn mg kg ⁻¹
Filter 45	10	71	1581	10	8.8	116	8.1	144	83
Filter 47	10	15	113	2.2	1.3	36	12	2.4	13
Filter 39	8	20	58	1.7	0.88	12	0.89	34	8.5
Filter 38	6.6	16	25	1	2.6	9.1	1.1	4.1	4.2
Filter 40	8.1	16	303	15	2.7	104	1.9	33	17
Filter 37	5.5	11	20	0.28	0.27	5.8	0.18	1.8	1.9
Filter 46	6.5	10	86	0.66	0.57	9.3	0.63	2.9	3.8
Filter 33	2.8	6.4	12	0.18	0.17	3.3	0.032	1	0.89

For filter 45, the results from microscopy and ICP-MS bulk analysis show good qualitative agreement, with S, Fe, Cu, Zn, Mn, and Cr identified by both techniques. For filter 47, agreement was observed for sulfur, Fe, and Ni; however, microscopy additionally identified Al and Si.

Microscopy techniques examine only a limited area of the filter and may therefore detect localised particulate deposits that are not representative of the entire sample. In contrast, ICP-MS analysis typically involves a much larger fraction of the filter (often approximately half), producing an averaged elemental composition. Consequently, discrepancies between microscopy and ICP-MS results may arise from sampling heterogeneity rather than from true analytical disagreement.

6. Conclusions

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2 This study delivers the first comprehensive field-based validation of hydrogen sampling
3 systems specifically adapted for HD refuelling applications. By testing multiple systems under
4 representative HD refuelling conditions, the work provides insight into sampling performance
5 at hydrogen refuelling stations.
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8 The results show that three sampling systems demonstrated equivalence for the majority of
9 regulated gaseous contaminants. This outcome supports their suitability for hydrogen quality
10 assessment in HD applications, provided they are deployed within comparative or
11 equivalence-based frameworks. The observed agreement across systems under dynamic
12 refuelling conditions is particularly relevant for current compliance verification approaches,
13 which often rely on relative performance rather than absolute reference measurements.
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17 Nevertheless, discrepancies identified for specific contaminants—most notably water and
18 sulfur compounds—reveal important limitations of equivalence testing alone. These species
19 are known to be sensitive to surface interactions, adsorption–desorption effects, and pressure
20 and temperature transients, all of which may differ between sampling configurations. The
21 results therefore underline the necessity of dedicated trueness evaluation strategies, including
22 recovery-based methods and traceable reference measurements, to complement equivalence
23 testing and ensure reliable quantification across the full range of regulated species.
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28 The comparative analysis between LD and HD sampling configurations further demonstrated
29 that hydrogen quality measured at one nozzle type cannot presently be used to infer fuel quality
30 at another. This outcome has direct implications for station monitoring strategies and
31 standardization efforts, indicating that nozzle-specific sampling approaches remain necessary
32 until more studies are performed.
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36 For particulate matter, the absence of clear correlations with refuelling parameters such as
37 pressure, mass flow, or refuelling duration suggests that the underlying generation and transport
38 mechanisms are more complex than can be resolved under the current test conditions. This
39 highlights the need for targeted experimental campaigns in which flow rate and pressure are
40 independently controlled, allowing the isolation of key contributing factors. Such experiments
41 would also support the development of harmonized particulate sampling methodologies for
42 hydrogen applications.
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46 Overall, this work represents a significant advancement toward robust hydrogen quality
47 assurance for HD transport. It provides experimental evidence to inform the ongoing evolution
48 of ISO 19880-9 and related standards, particularly with respect to sampling system
49 qualification, applicability limits, and validation procedures.
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53 Future research should prioritize the development of reference facilities capable of delivering
54 traceable contaminant levels under HD-relevant operating conditions. Recovery-based
55 approaches, combined with reference materials and standardized protocols, will be essential to
56 establish sampling trueness across all regulated contaminants. Such efforts will be critical to
57 ensuring confidence in hydrogen quality measurements as HD hydrogen refuelling
58 infrastructure continues to expand.
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